

Fig. 1. Ir spectra of samples : (○) Co-Mo, (■) Ni-Mo, (×) Cu-Mo, (●) Ag-Mo and (—) Bi-Mo.

TABLE 1—Mo=O IR BANDS OF THE SAMPLES AND ACTIVATION ENERGIES (E_a) FOR THE OXIDATION OF O
Flow rate=166 ml/min⁻¹

Sample	$\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ cm ⁻¹	E_a kcal mol ⁻¹
Silver molybdate	820	3.0
Cobalt molybdate	940	1.0
Nickel molybdate	940	1.0
Copper molybdate	850	2.6
Bismuth molybdate	840	2.6

the combination as the former is a better Lewis acid⁶.

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Study of the Effect of Storing Time on Oscillatory Reaction involving Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid

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OSCILLATORY chemical reaction involving several organic substrates has been the subject of investigation¹⁻⁵. It was observed in our study⁶ that acetone dicarboxylic acid drives the system oscillatory. It was further observed that the oxidation of citric acid by ceric salt produced acetone dicarboxylic acid (ADA) in aqueous solution (hereafter, solution A*) according to the equation,

Solution A* responded well⁶ in the oscillatory system when it replaced freshly prepared acetone dicarboxylic acid. The present communication reports the effect of storing the ingredients of solution A* to various lengths of time.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade (B.D.H). The stock solutions of 0.056 M citric acid and 0.1M Ce^{IV} sulphate were prepared in 1.5M sulphuric acid medium. Potassium bromate (Baker, A.R.) was dried at 120°. A 0.03M solution of KBrO₃ was prepared in 1.5 M sulphuric acid. The ingredients of solution A*, i.e. 0.056 M citric acid (10 ml) and

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TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS ON STORAGE TIME OF SOLUTION A*

[ADA]=0.0056 M, [Ce^{III}]=0.005 M, [KBrO₃]=0.03 M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5 M

Storage time (hrs)	20°						26°						
	t_{in}		t		t_1		t_{in}		t		t_1		A mV
	min	s	min	s	min	s	min	s	min	s	min	s	
2	4'	45"	2'	50"	70'		3'	25"	2'	20"	53'		90
4	21'		1'		43'								40
8	18'		2'	10"	155'		15'	50"	1'	30"	110'		60
∞	21'		10'		120'		18'	30"	8'		130'		-300

0.1M Ce^{VI} sulphate (1.1 ml) were mixed and stored in a thermostat at a required temperature for the desired length of time (*viz.* 2, 4, 8 h or infinite time). Each solution A* was used to study the oscillatory characteristics along with 0.03 M potassium bromate solution (10 ml). The e.m.f. values were measured every 5 s with the help of a digital potentiometer.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the variation of time of initiation (t_{in}), time period (t) and life-time (t_1) of oscillations, when the solution A* containing acetone dicarboxylic acid was stored at different lengths of time at the temperatures $20 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and $26 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

The time of initiation of oscillations increased very sharply as the components of solution A* were allowed to stand for successively more time period at any temperature. This delay in the onset of oscillations may be due to the fact that the system requires time to accumulate sufficient amount of brominated organic species which can trigger off the oscillations. Acetone dicarboxylic acid decomposes⁷ very easily on standing to acetone, a non-promoter of oscillations. The longer the time the solution A* was stored the lesser would be the amount of compound effective in oscillation. Acetone is known to get brominated easily⁸ and thus consumes the major portions of reacting bromine species like Br⁻, BrO₃⁻ and HBrO₂, thereby leaving very little of them for bromination of acetone dicarboxylic acid and other compounds (which might have been formed) that help to promote the oscillations. This also increases the time period of oscillations gradually, as oscillations did exist in the cases of a weak old solutions A* (tagged infinite time) but were least frequent (Table 1).

The amplitude of oscillations showd a general decreasing trend with the increase in storage time, so much so that for the solutions stored infinitely, there was sharp drop in potential of the systems giving rise to sort of inverted peaks. The oscillations are well defined and were most prominent in case of 2 h storing of solution A* as the amount of acetone dicarboxylic acid was maximum, but this amount gradually decreased with the length of storing.

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Isothermal Diffusion Coefficient of Tetra-alkylammonium Salts in Aqueous Solutions

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THE present communication reports the isothermal diffusion coefficients (D) of tetraethylammonium chloride and bromide, as well as those of tetra-*n*-butylammonium bromide and nitrate in aqueous solutions at 35 and 40°. A Stokes' type of diaphragm diffusion cell^{1,2} has been used for the purpose with the following working relation²,

$$D = \frac{1}{\beta t} \ln \frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_3 - C_4} \quad (1)$$

where, D is the (double average) diaphragm cell integral diffusion coefficient, β is the cell constant, and $(C_1 - C_2)$ and $(C_3 - C_4)$ are the initial and final (*i.e.*, after time t) concentration differences between the cell compartments.

In order to check the reliability of the present results in terms of the Stokes-Einstein equation for temperature dependence of D , the viscosity coefficients (η) of the solutions used have been measured at 35 and 40° by using a Ubbelohde viscometer³.

Experimental

Diffusion experiments: The diaphragm cell used for measuring diffusion coefficient was similar to